

AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF RECEIVING TEACHER PRACTICES FOR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE CLASSROOMS

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An In-Depth Analysis of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with Special Educational Needs in Inclusive Classrooms

Vexilla Cecilia M. Marinay,* Niña Rozanne T. Delos Reyes

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research assessed the effectiveness of receiving teacher practices in supporting students with special educational needs (SEN) and explored student progress at Talisay City National High School for the school year 2023-2024. A descriptive-correlational design was employed to examine the relationship between the extent of inclusive teacher practices and student progress. The sample consisted of 47 respondents selected through simple random sampling from the population of receiving teachers. The data were analyzed using the following statistical tools: frequency counts and percentages for demographic profiles, weighted mean for evaluating the extent of inclusive teacher practices and student progress, and the Pearson-r correlation test to determine significant relationships. The study found that most respondents were aged 31 to 37, had Master's units, and 6-10 years of teaching experience. Collaboration, progress monitoring, pedagogical support, and psychological assistance between receiving and special education teachers were often practiced, indicating a strong commitment to inclusive education for students with special educational needs (SEN). The researcher concluded that a comprehensive, collaborative teaching approach, continuous progress monitoring, targeted pedagogical support, and psychological assistance significantly benefit students with special educational needs in inclusive settings. It is highly recommended to adopt the Action Plan on Inclusive Education as a foundation for teacher training and professional development to enhance the holistic development of these students.

Keywords: *special education, inclusive education, collaboration, monitoring progress, pedagogical support*

Introduction

Inclusion goes beyond merely placing students with disabilities in mainstream classrooms; it involves adapting teaching methods, curriculum, and support systems to meet the diverse needs of all learners. It also involves raising awareness, building positive attitudes, and challenging stereotypes to create an inclusive culture within educational institutions and society as a whole. A child has a right to inclusive education; it is not a privilege. Without excluding anyone, inclusion supports equitable and high-quality education for all students, including those who might be excluded due to their learning needs or social standing. The concept of inclusive education was developed in response to a growing understanding of disabled children's rights to receive the same educational services as children without disabilities (UNESCO International Bureau of Education, 2009 as cited in Global Education Monitoring Report, 2020).

The Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994) adamantly demands inclusivity, which encourages countries to establish a plan of action for promoting equity and inclusion through the education of students who have visible differences. The world has committed to inclusive education for a reason—it is the cornerstone of a high-quality educational system that enables every child, adolescent, and adult to learn and reach their full potential (Global Education Monitoring Report, 2020). It is widely acknowledged that inclusive education provides all students with equal access and opportunities, cultural and historical factors make all countries' educational policies and reform initiatives unique (Savolainen et al., 2012 as cited in Yada and Savolainen, 2017).

All children can learn given the right environment, as stated in Brunei Darussalam's special education policy guidelines, which were adopted in 1994. Its special education philosophy places a strong emphasis on the need to provide all children with special needs with educational opportunities in order for them to reach their full potential as contributing members of society. Malaysia has developed special and inclusive education for students with disabilities as a result of a worldwide inclusion movement. Special schools, the Special Education Integrated Program (SEIP), and the Inclusive Program are the three different kinds of special education programs. The Inclusive Program places students with disabilities in regular classes (Ministry of Education, 2004 as cited in Global Education Monitoring Report, 2020). In the Philippines, the Department of Education issued DO No. 26, s. 1997, which requires the establishment of Special Education (SPED) Programs in all schools. It was stated that all divisions shall organize at least one SPED Center which will cater children with special needs. As a signatory to the Salamanca statement, the Philippines has implemented a few laws to advance inclusion, and most recently, the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" was passed, which categorically mandates that all Filipino teachers include their students in their lessons (Department of Education, 2013 as cited in Raguindin et al., 2020). When implementing inclusive education, receiving teachers often encounter several challenges. One major issue is the lack of sufficient training and professional development in inclusive education and special needs. This can create uncertainty and insecurity when teaching students with diverse learning needs. Additionally, inclusive classrooms frequently have a high student-to-teacher ratio, which can be overwhelming and hinder the ability to offer personalized support to each student.

Moreover, students with special needs have diverse learning requirements, necessitating that receiving teachers adapt their methods to meet these needs. Differentiated instruction can be challenging and time-consuming, and students with special needs may exhibit

challenging behaviors in mainstream classrooms. This makes inclusive education emotionally and mentally taxing for teachers, leading to stress and burnout. These challenges must be addressed to ensure successful inclusion. Receiving teachers play a crucial role and must practice collaboration, progress monitoring, pedagogical support, and psychological assistance. Addressing these issues requires a collaborative effort among teachers, administrators, support staff, and the school community. Essential steps include providing ongoing training, fostering a culture of inclusion, and encouraging open communication. Including students with Special Educational Needs (SENs) in regular classrooms poses challenges, but effective collaboration between Special Education (SpEd) teachers and mainstream educators can provide these students with the support and opportunities they need to succeed academically and socially. Responsibility for their success doesn't solely rest on SpEd teachers but requires a collective effort. Both SpEd and receiving teachers must acknowledge their shared responsibility for the progress of students with SENs, fostering teamwork and mutual ownership of each student's development across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Given the diverse characteristics of students with special needs, including cognitive, affective, and psychomotor differences from typically developing peers, ongoing monitoring ensures they receive necessary support and accommodations to fully engage in the learning process within an inclusive education framework.

In Talisay City National High School of Talisay City Division, it has been observed that the school has a particular learning center that incorporates inclusive practices within schools and crucial responsibilities and strategies for fostering inclusivity in the classroom. Despite efforts to include students with special needs in regular classrooms, receiving teachers still face significant challenges. Many lack the necessary training and experience to effectively support these students within inclusive settings. Additionally, there is often a lack of coordination with specialists and experts who can provide additional guidance and resources. These issues are complex and require careful attention. It's essential to address them effectively to ensure that all students, including those with special needs, can succeed both academically and socially in inclusive classrooms. By improving training, providing better support systems, and fostering collaboration among teachers and specialists, schools can create an environment where every student has the opportunity to thrive. This approach not only benefits students with special needs but enhances the overall educational experience for everyone involved.

This research assessed the effectiveness of receiving teacher practices in supporting students with special educational needs (SEN) and explored student's level of progress at Talisay City National High School in Talisay City Division for the school year 2023-2024 as the basis for an Action Plan on Inclusive Education.

Research Questions

This research evaluated the effectiveness of various receiving teacher practices in supporting students with special educational needs (SEN) in inclusive classroom and explored the student's level of progress of Talisay City National High School in Talisay City Division for the school year 2023-2024 as the basis for an Action Plan on Inclusive Education. It sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.3. years of teaching experience;
 - 1.4. number of students in class; and
 - 1.5. related seminars and trainings attended?
2. What is the extent of receiving teacher practices for students with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms in terms of:
 - 2.1. collaboration;
 - 2.2. monitoring progress;
 - 2.3. pedagogical support; and
 - 2.4. psychosocial assistance?
3. What is the level of student's progress with special educational needs in terms of:
 - 3.1. affective;
 - 3.2. cognitive; and
 - 3.3. psychomotor domain?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the receiving teacher practices and the progress of students with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms?
5. What action plan can be crafted based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

This study theorizes that the receiving teacher practices could influence the level of progress of the students with special educational needs. This is supported by the theory of behaviorism of Watson, 1913, cognitivism of Piaget, 1950 and constructivism of Vygotsky, 1978.

Inclusion of students with special educational needs and students without disabilities in mainstream settings is known as inclusive education. To fulfill the varied requirements of all learners, it entails modifying instructional strategies, curricula, and support structures. To develop an inclusive culture within educational institutions and society at large, it also entails raising awareness,

cultivating positive attitudes, and confronting misconceptions. According to behaviorism theory, learning is associated with modifications in the nature or frequency of perceptible performance. They think that reinforcement or rewards from the environment determine how people behave. When the right reaction to a particular environmental event is shown, learning has taken place. As a result, there is a direct connection between behavioral responses and stimulus in the process of learning Al-Shammari (2019) discovered that behaviorist instructional strategies, which are supported by evidence and demonstrate significant effects in enhancing the learning and achievement of students with special needs in inclusive elementary schools, are integral to professional development for in-service special education teachers and teacher education programs in Kuwait. Moreover, inclusive education practices best serve the needs of all students, including those with special needs by adopting an eclectic approach to the use of theory-driven inclusive education which comprised of behaviorism, cognitivism and constructivism (Al-Shammari et. al, 2019).

Cognitive theories are more in line with the rationalist end of the epistemology continuum since they place a strong emphasis on knowledge acquisition and internal mental processes (Bower and Hilgard 1981 as cited in Ertmer and Newby, 2013), cognitive theories are more in line with the rationalist end of the epistemology continuum since they place a strong emphasis on knowledge acquisition and internal mental processes. Learning is compared to discrete changes in knowledge rather than variations in response probability. Cognitive theories are concerned with how students conceptualize their learning processes and how the mind receives, organizes, stores, and retrieves information.

In Cognitivism, it comprises scientific study on the signs of mental life in as much as it relates to how people think when learning, digesting impressions brought in by the senses, resolving conflicts, and recalling skills and work methods required in daily life (Muhajirah,2020). Cognitive, affective, and conative symptoms, or psychosomatics, are all a part of mental life and cannot be isolated from one another. As a result, cognitive psychology investigates not only the causes of typical cognitive symptoms but also those arising from the affective (the interpretation and consideration that accompany the reaction of sensations) and conative (will decisions) domains.

The application of theory-driven inclusive education that incorporates behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism in inclusive education methods best serves the needs of all children, including those with special needs (Al-Shammari et al., 2019). The goal of constructivism is to develop cognitive tools that both capture and convey the knowledge of the culture in which they are utilized. Constructivism entails an individual comprehending the significance of the social component during the learning process through observation, treatment, interpretation, and adaptation of information on developing a cognitive structure.

A constructivist classroom places a strong emphasis on active learning, collaboration, looking at a concept or problem from various angles, reflection, student-centeredness, and genuine evaluation to encourage meaningful learning and aid students in building their own worldviews. Constructivism-based inclusive education practices emphasized making learning more meaningful and using real-life experiences (Al-Shammari et al.,2019)

Inclusive education is about recognizing and valuing the diversity of all students while providing the necessary support and accommodations to ensure their success. Republic Act No. 11650, also known as the "Inclusive Education Act," is a significant piece of legislation in the Philippines that underscores the government's commitment to promoting inclusive education for all children, regardless of their abilities, disabilities, or differences. This law seeks to ensure that students with disabilities (SWDs) and those with special educational needs (SEN) have equal access to quality education and are fully integrated into regular school environments. The Inclusive Education Act is rooted in the principle of inclusivity. It recognizes that all children, regardless of their abilities, have the right to access quality education in mainstream schools. Inclusion means that students with disabilities are educated alongside their non-disabled peers whenever possible.

Moreover, Republic Act No. 7277, also known as the "Magna Carta for Disabled Persons," is a significant piece of legislation in the Philippines that aims to promote and protect the rights and welfare of individuals with disabilities. This law reflects the government's commitment to ensuring that persons with disabilities (PWDs) enjoy equal opportunities, participate fully in society, and lead meaningful lives. RA 7277 mandates that PWDs should have equal access to opportunities in education, employment, and other aspects of life. It prohibits discrimination on the basis of disability and promotes a barrier-free environment to accommodate the needs of PWDs. Moreover, the law promotes inclusive education, ensuring that PWDs have the right to an accessible and appropriate education. Special education programs are established to support the learning needs of PWDs, and discrimination against PWD students is prohibited.

DepEd Order No. 72, series of 2009, titled "Inclusive Education as Strategy for Increasing Participation Rate," is an important policy document issued by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines. This order emphasizes the significance of inclusive education as a strategy to improve the overall participation rate of students, particularly those who are vulnerable or have special educational needs. It underscores the DepEd's commitment to promoting inclusive education in the Philippine education system. It also recognizes that access to education is a fundamental right for all children, regardless of their abilities or circumstances. Moreover, DepEd Order No. 72 encourages the mainstreaming of students with special needs into regular classrooms whenever possible. It suggests that students with disabilities can benefit from being educated alongside their non-disabled peers, provided that appropriate support and accommodations are in place. By emphasizing the principles of inclusivity, equity, and non-discrimination, this order seeks to increase the participation rate of all students in the educational system and create a more inclusive learning environment.

Teaching in an inclusive education setting requires a variety of strategies to ensure that students with diverse needs and abilities can access the curriculum and thrive in the classroom. Teaching strategies are the methods, approaches, and techniques that educators use to facilitate learning and help students acquire knowledge and skills such as differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, peer teaching, etc. Effective teaching strategies are essential for engaging students, supporting their understanding, and promoting a positive learning experience.

Creating inclusive classroom and school practices are essential for the successful inclusion of students with special needs. Teachers providing differentiated instruction to meet the diverse needs of students is one of the inclusive classroom practices that has been in practice. Additionally, collaborative teaching is another example where a general education teacher and a special education teacher work together to support all students. On the other hand, the inclusive school practices could include professional development for teachers and staff on inclusive education practices, disability awareness, and effective support strategies; and parents and guardians' involvement in decision-making and planning for their child's education. These practices promote a welcoming and supportive environment where all students, regardless of their abilities, can learn and thrive. Consequently, the practices in inclusive classes are characterized by a higher connection to the students' living environment, a stronger focus on students' interests, the use of new teaching methods and ensuring that weaker pupils also benefit from lessons (Paseka and Schwab, 2020).

According to Bryant, et al., 2019, collaboration is the key ingredient of the effort of inclusive schools to meet the needs of the students in different settings and activities. It ensures that all students, including those with special needs, receive the support and resources necessary to achieve their full potential. It creates a more inclusive, supportive, and equitable educational environment, fostering the academic and personal growth of all students. Moreover, it is thought that classroom teachers working in mainstreaming class should receive support services in order to develop themselves in collaboration with experts and these services will positively affect mainstreaming education (Batu, 2000 as cited in Paseka & Schwab, 2020). According Gokbulut et al. (2020), the co-teaching practices in all-inclusive environments had positive effects on the development of students' comprehension skills and that these practices responded to the students' academic and social needs.

On the other hand, pedagogical support is fundamental to the success of inclusive education. It ensures that students with special needs receive the personalized instruction and support they need to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. By recognizing and addressing the diverse needs of these students, pedagogical support contributes to a more inclusive and equitable education system where all students have the opportunity to learn and grow. Ahmet (2021) found out the mainstreaming class teachers regarding the teaching methods and activities of the students, it can be distinguished that the teachers provided one on-one support to the students with special needs. The teachers assign various activities to other students in the classroom to assist learners with special needs using visual materials created by the support education teacher and themselves. Mitchell and Sutherland (2020) found consistent evidence that inclusive educational settings- those in which children with disabilities are educated alongside their non-disabled peers can confer substantial short- and long-term benefits for children's cognitive and social development.

It can also be noted that providing psychosocial assistance for students with special needs in inclusive education is crucial for their well-being and academic success Mjelve et al. (2019) emphasized the necessity of support systems for children experiencing psychosocial challenges that may indicate more serious issues, even if they do not yet meet the criteria for special needs services. It involves addressing their social, emotional, and psychological needs to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

Monitoring students' learning and progress is a fundamental aspect of effective education. It benefits students, teachers, parents, and the educational system as a whole by fostering individualized instruction, improving outcomes, and ensuring accountability and equity in education. Ahmet (2021) emphasized the importance of continuous information about the learner's progress through daily, weekly and annual meetings, In the context of inclusive education, monitoring helps ensure that students with disabilities or special needs receive the appropriate support and accommodations to participate fully in the learning process.

Methodology

Research Design

A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them (Bhandari, 2023). Thus, this study used a descriptive correlational design to determine the relationship between the extent of inclusive teacher practices and students' level of progress. The number of respondents was determined using simple random sampling. Finally, the data were analyzed using the following statistical tools: frequency counts and percentages for demographic profiles, weighted mean for evaluating the extent of inclusive teacher practices and student progress, and the Pearson-r correlation test to determine significant relationships.

Respondents

In determining the respondents of the study, the teachers handling students with special educational needs in the inclusive classrooms of Talisay City National High School were selected. Receiving teachers, comprising advisers and subject teachers in both Junior High School and Senior High School, play a pivotal role in the integration of SEN students, actively shaping their daily educational experiences. Their firsthand insights and experiences are invaluable for understanding the complexities and achievements of inclusive

education, highlighting their essential role in this research. In ensuring the validity and reliability of the samples, simple random sampling was utilized.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Receiving Teachers</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Junior High School	30	63.83
Senior High School	17	36.17
Total	47	100.00

Instruments

The questionnaire was composed of three parts: the demographic profile of the students, the extent of inclusive teacher practices and the student's level of progress. The researcher utilized a questionnaire adapted from the study of Suzanne Ripley on her thesis entitled "Collaboration between General and Special Education Teacher and DepEd Order 44, s. 2021, titled "Policy Guidelines on the Provision of Educational Programs and Services for Learners with Disabilities in the K-12 Basic Education Program. To ensure the adapted questionnaire was suitable for our study context, it underwent a validation process involving experts in inclusive education like the SpEd teacher in the school. In the context of inclusive education, tools like assessments, progress monitoring instruments, and feedback mechanisms are vital for evaluating the effectiveness of educational practices and student outcomes. The factors of collaboration, monitoring progress, pedagogical support, and psychosocial support play significant roles in determining how frequently these instruments should be used.

A Likert scale of the extent of inclusive teacher practices and student's level of progress were used. The scale of the level of frequency was used to measure the extent of inclusive teacher practices in terms of Collaboration, Monitoring Progress, Pedagogical Support, and Psychosocial Support. On the other hand, the scale of the level of Proficiency was used to measure the level of progress of the students with SEN. The researcher categorized the frequency and proficiency levels as follows: (5) always/proficient, (4) often/approaching proficiency, (3) sometimes/developing, (2) rarely/beginning, and (1) never/not applicable.

Procedure

The data were gathered through the several processes:

Preliminary Stage. The researchers asked permission from the school research coordinator and the school head of the Talisay City National High School through a transmittal letter. After ensuring that the research tool was already valid and reliable, informed consent for the respondents of the study was secured on a voluntary basis.

Data Gathering Stage. The researcher carried out a thorough face-to-face orientation session with the receiving teacher and the subject teachers involved in the study. The orientation process included the following steps: (1) Explanation of Study Objectives and Procedures (2) Ethical Protocols, and (3) Distribution and Completion of Questionnaires. Respondents were allowed ample time to complete the survey questionnaire at their convenience, and the completed questionnaires were subsequently collected.

Post Data Gathering Stage. Tabulation of the data was done after the retrieval of the questionnaires. All the gathered data were encoded in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and subjected to statistical computation with the help of the statistician. Then, the last step was the interpretation, analysis, and presentation of the data.

Data Analysis

The data that was gathered through the survey questionnaire was tabulated, organized, and analyzed. Additionally, the data were treated and analyzed using the subsequent statistical tools:

Frequency Count. This was used to tally the number of respondents' responses on their demographic profile. By counting each response, the researcher could easily summarize and present participants' characteristics such as age, gender, educational background, and teaching experience. This method helps organize and understand data distribution.

Percentage. This was used to determine the proportion of respondents within each demographic category. Calculating percentages provides a clearer understanding of the sample's composition, highlighting the prevalence of specific characteristics and aiding in comparing category representation.

Weighted Mean. This was used to assess the extent of inclusive teacher practices and students' progress levels. By assigning weights to Likert scale responses, the weighted mean offers a more accurate overall rating. It considers varying degrees of agreement or proficiency, providing a comprehensive measure of inclusive practices and student progress.

Pearson's r. This was used to determine the relationship between the extent of inclusive teacher practices and students' progress levels. Pearson's correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. By calculating Pearson's r, the researcher could identify significant correlations, offering insights into the effectiveness of inclusive education strategies.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the study, the researcher followed strict ethical guidelines and standards. The study received thorough review and approval from the ethical review board before proceeding. The researcher ensured that all research activities, particularly data collection through survey questionnaires, adhered to the highest human rights and safety standards. Participants' rights were clearly communicated, and the researcher took steps to protect respondents from unintended harm through confidentiality and informed consent.

Participants were required to provide informed consent prior to the study, confirming their full understanding of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The research was carried out with the utmost honesty and integrity, with no fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism involved. Additionally, students were assured that all study materials would be securely removed once the course was completed.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses and interpretations of the data gathered from the study which aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, number of students handled per classroom and seminars/trainings attended. This also assesses the extent of receiving teacher practices for students with SEN in inclusive classroom in terms of Collaboration, Monitoring Progress, Pedagogical Support and Psychosocial Assistance towards the level of progress of student with SEN in terms of Affective, Cognitive and Psychomotor domain. Furthermore, the relationship between extent of receiving teacher practices and the level of progress of students with SEN was also considered.

The following conclusions and findings are presented and discussed using the responses of the respondents to the survey questionnaire:

Profile of the Respondents

This section presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, parents' highest educational attainment, and combined family monthly income.

Age and Gender

Age and gender are considered important variables that need to be determined in this study which could help in explaining the results of the study. Data gathered are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Age and Gender of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
52-58	3					
45-51	5	6.38	1	2.13	4	8.51
38-44	10	10.63	0	0	5	10.63
	12	21.28	1	2.13	11	23.41
31-37	10	25.53	2	4.26	14	29.79
24-30	40	21.28	3	6.38	13	27.66
Total		85.10	7	14.90	134	100.00

As shown in Table 2, there were 40 out of 47 respondents who are female teachers which comprised 85.10 percent of the respondents. Twelve or 25.53 percent of the female teachers were 31-37 years old followed by 38-44 years old and 24-30 years old which have ten female teachers for each age bracket. Moreover, there were five or 10.63 percent of them whose age were 45-51 and three or 6.38 percent of them whose age were 52-58 years old.

On the other hand, there were only seven or 14.90 percent of them were male teachers. The implication regarding the age and gender of teachers in handling students in inclusive education suggests that diverse demographic factors may contribute to varied perspectives, teaching approaches, and communication styles. While age and gender can influence teaching methods, it is essential to recognize that effective handling of students in inclusive education is primarily determined by a combination of factors, including pedagogical skills, empathy, and a commitment to inclusive practices. Saloviita (2020) discovered that teachers' attitudes towards inclusion were influenced by their age and gender. Additionally, younger teachers had a somewhat more favorable attitude toward inclusion, and female teachers exhibited slightly more positive feelings about inclusion compared to their male counterparts (Saloviita, 2020).

Teacher's Highest Educational Attainment

Teacher's highest level of education attained is regarded as a crucial variable that must be established for this study in order to support the findings. Data gathered are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3. *Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Doctoral Degree	2	4.26
With Doctoral units	2	4.26
Master's Degree	4	8.51
With Master's units	29	61.70
Bachelor's Degree	10	21.27
Total	47	100.00

As shown in Table 3, most of the teachers' highest educational attainment were "with Master's units" in which there were 29 or 61.70 percent. Moreover, there were only two teachers in the Doctoral degree and with Doctoral units as their highest educational attainment.

Teachers with higher educational attainment, such as advanced degrees in special education or related fields, may bring specialized knowledge and research-based practices to inclusive classrooms. This advanced training could equip them with a more comprehensive understanding of diverse learning needs and effective instructional strategies tailored to students with Special Educational Needs (SEN). Teacher competencies in accommodating students with special educational needs (SEN) in regular classrooms are crucial, not only for effective inclusive practices but also because they influence teacher attitudes toward inclusive education. (Pit-ten Cate, 2018).

Years of Teaching Experience

The years of teaching experience is viewed as a vital variable that must be recognized for this study in order to support the findings. Data gathered are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. *Years of Teaching Experience*

<i>Teaching Experience (in years)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
21 years and above	4	8.51
16-20 years	5	10.64
11-15 years	5	10.64
6-10 years	17	36.17
0-5 years	16	34.04
Total	47	100.00

As shown in Table 4, 17 or 36.17 percent of the teachers has 6-10 years of teaching experience followed by 0-5 years in which there were 16 or 34.04 percent. Moreover, five or 10.64% has 11-15 years and another five teachers has 16-20 years of teaching experience. Lastly, only 4 or 8.51% have 21 years and above teaching experience.

Experienced teachers may benefit from accumulated knowledge and diverse experiences, allowing them to navigate the complexities of inclusive education more adeptly. Their familiarity with various teaching strategies, classroom management techniques, and individualized approaches may contribute to creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Younger, less experienced teachers without special education training showed less enthusiasm about the benefits of inclusion, doubted their ability to manage integrated classrooms, and felt less confident in teaching students with disabilities (Mngo and Mngo, 2018).

Number of Students in Class

The number of students per class is a significant factor in the overall effectiveness of teaching and learning. Hence, it must be included in this study in order to support the findings. Data gathered are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5. *Number of students in class*

<i>No. of Students</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
63-70	25	53.19
55-62	13	27.66
47-54	9	19.15
Total	47	100.00

As shown in Table 5, most teachers were handling 63-70 students and that is 25 or 53.19 percent which is more than half of the respondents. While 13 or 27.66 percent were handling 55-62 students and 9 or 19.15 percent were handling 47-54 students in a classroom. Larger class sizes may present difficulties in providing the necessary level of individualized support. Teachers in larger classes might find it challenging to differentiate instruction and address the unique learning styles and requirements of each student. This could potentially hinder the inclusivity and responsiveness of the educational environment. Bartak and Fry (2004) discovered that students exhibited learning difficulties and behavior problems, leading teachers to view them as requiring significant support that they were unable to provide without additional assistance.

Seminars/Trainings in Special Education

Seminars and training in Special Education are essential for teachers to obtain the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to meet the

different needs of children with disabilities, develop inclusive learning environments, and promote equitable educational opportunities for all. Data gathered are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6. *Seminars/Trainings in Special Education*

<i>Seminars/Trainings</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Learning Action Cell (LAC)	13	27.66
SPED Seminars/Trainings	2	4.25
None	32	68.09
Total	47	100.00

Table 6 depicts that the majority of teachers—32, or 68.09 percent—do not have a seminar or training in a mainstream classroom. Furthermore, just thirteen teachers, or 27.66 percent, have attended a learning action cell to learn how to work with students who have special needs in a mainstream classroom. Receiving teachers who undergo specialized training and attend seminars on inclusive education are likely to acquire a deeper understanding of diverse learning profiles, teaching strategies, and individualized support methods. This enhanced knowledge base enables them to create more accessible and accommodating learning environments that foster the success of students with SEN. Crispel and Kasperski (2021) highlighted the necessity of training teachers within mainstream educational frameworks to adequately address the special needs of their students and recommended incorporating this knowledge into all teacher education programs, rather than confining it to special-education teachers, to advance inclusive education.

Extent of Receiving Teachers’ Practices

This section presents the extent of receiving teacher practices for students with SEN in inclusive classroom in terms of Collaboration, Monitoring Progress, Pedagogical Support and Psychosocial Assistance which are presented in Table 7,8,9 and 10, respectively.

Table 7. *Extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN In Inclusive Classroom in terms of Collaboration*

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1	Works collaboratively with a teacher in special education to combine professional knowledge, perspectives, and skills.	3.96	1.04	Often
2	Maintain joint responsibilities for specified special education instruction.	4.11	1.03	Often
3	Share resources and materials to support the learning needs of SPED students.	3.64	1.21	Often
4	Share training and expertise in teaching techniques and learning processes.	3.60	1.10	Often
5	Collaborative planning sessions for the development of strategies, accommodations, and modifications tailored to the needs of SPED students.	3.55	1.19	Often
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.77		Often
Aggregate Standard Deviation			1.11	

Legend: 4.21-5.00- Always; 3.41-4.20- Often ; 2.61-3.40- Sometimes ; 1.81-2.60-Rarely; 1.00-1.80- Never

Table 7 shows the extent of receiving teacher practices for students with SEN in inclusive classroom in terms of Collaboration. The data reveals that item 2 got the highest weighted mean of 4.11 which indicates “Often”. This implies that receiving teachers and the SpEd teacher often collaborate in maintaining a joint responsibility to students with SEN. On the other hand, item 5 has the lowest weighted mean of 3.55 though still indicates as “Often” which may imply that planning sessions of the receiving teachers and the SpEd teacher is of less priority among other indicators. With an average weighted mean and a standard deviation of 4.51 and 0.94, respectively, the teaching methods used in mainstream classrooms regarding collaboration are generally visible. The joint responsibility implies that both receiving and SpEd teachers actively engage in the design and implementation of individualized strategies, accommodations, and interventions. This collective effort can enhance the overall learning experience for students with diverse needs, promoting their academic and social development. Effective collaboration in teaching responsibilities is pivotal for success, necessitating transitions from coordination to cooperation and reflective communication. This requires transformation efforts from individual educators, alongside a shared vision for inclusive future activities and systemic changes in school practices (Paju et al., 2022).

Table 8. *Extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN in Inclusive Classroom in terms of Monitoring Progress*

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1	Maintains open and ongoing communication which includes sharing information about student’s progress and challenges.	4.06	1.07	Often
2	Regularly exchanged data on student performance and progress.	3.94	1.15	Often
3	Provide feedback to the students and their parents regarding progress.	3.87	1.17	Often
4	Keep records of student’s data and observations to have a historical view of progress.	4.04	0.95	Often
5	Review progress on a regular basis, make adjustments, evaluate students, and develop strategies to address problems either in discipline or learning. .	4.15	0.96	Often
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.01	1.06	Often
Aggregate Standard Deviation			1.06	

Legend: 4.21-5.00- Always; 3.41-4.20- Often ; 2.61-3.40- Sometimes ; 1.81-2.60-Rarely; 1.00-1.80- Never

Table 8 presents the level of receiving teacher practices in terms of progress monitoring for students with SEN in inclusive classrooms. Item 5, which depicts frequent interactions between the special education teacher and the receiving teachers, had the highest weighted mean of 4.28. However, item 3 is the lowest weighted mean of 3.87, suggesting that there are rarely apparent practices between the special education teacher and the receiving teachers. When it comes to tracking student achievement, the weighted average and standard deviation of the instructional strategies used in the mainstream classroom are typically 4.01 and 1.06, respectively. The rarity of apparent receiving teacher practices in terms of progress monitoring for students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in inclusive classrooms suggests a potential gap in individualized support and intervention. This may imply a need for increased emphasis on systematic and ongoing monitoring strategies to better understand and address the unique learning trajectories of students with SEN within inclusive settings. Implementing systematic and evidence-based progress monitoring practices supports a dynamic and responsive learning environment in mainstream classrooms. DuFour et al. (2016) suggested that teacher collaboration and data-driven decision-making contribute to more effective monitoring of student progress.

Table 9. *Extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN In Inclusive Classroom in terms of Pedagogical Support*

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Allow flexible pacing for SPED students to accommodate their individual learning rate.	4.15	0.98	Often
2	Adapt teaching methods and materials to accommodate diverse learning styles, abilities, and preferences among SPED students.	4.15	0.98	Often
3	Integrate assistive technologies and tools, such as speech-to-text software, screen readers, or communication devices.	3.32	1.24	Sometimes
4	Provide clear and explicit instructions, breaking down complex tasks into smaller, manageable steps to support comprehension and learning.	4.06	1.03	Often
5	Encourage peer support and cooperative learning opportunities where SPED students can work with their peers to achieve common goals.	4.28	1.04	Always
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.01		Often
Aggregate Standard Deviation			3.99	

Legend: 4.21-5.00- Always; 3.41-4.20- Often ; 2.61-3.40- Sometimes ; 1.81-2.60-Rarely; 1.00-1.80- Never

The extent of receiving teacher practices for students with SEN in inclusive classroom in terms of pedagogical support is presented in Table 9. The data reveals that item 5, which represents often seen interactions between the receiving teachers and the special education teacher, had the highest weighted mean of 4.28. However, item 3 has the lowest weighted mean of 3.32, indicating that there are occasionally noticeable practices between the receiving teachers and the special education teacher. In general, the weighted average and standard deviation of the mainstream classroom's teaching methods are generally 3.99 and 0.77, respectively, making them often visible in terms of pedagogical support. The occasional visibility of receiving teacher practices for students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in terms of pedagogical support, in collaboration with the Special Education (SpEd) teacher, suggests a need for increased attention to tailored instructional strategies within inclusive classrooms. While the practices are noticeable at times, there may be room for enhancing the consistency of collaborative pedagogical support to better meet the diverse learning needs of students with SEN. Pedagogical support plays a crucial role in fostering inclusive education by addressing diverse learning needs. Friend and Bursuck (2018) emphasized the significance of collaborative teaching strategies, highlighting that co-teaching models enhance instructional effectiveness for students with varied abilities.

Table 10. *Extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN in Inclusive Classroom in terms of Psychosocial Assistance*

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Foster an inclusive classroom environment where all students, including those with special education needs, are respected, valued, and included in all aspects of classroom life.	4.51	0.93	Always
2	Encourage peer support by pairing students with special educational needs with classroom buddies or peer mentors.	4.49	1.04	Always
3	Consider flexible seating arrangements that allow SPED students to sit in a location that is conducive to their learning and social interactions.	4.47	1.04	Always
4	Use positive reinforcement and praise to recognize and celebrate the achievements and progress of SPED students, reinforcing their self-esteem and motivation.	4.51	0.88	Always
5	Be culturally sensitive and inclusive, respecting the cultural backgrounds and identities of all students, including those with special educational needs.	4.55	0.83	Always
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.01		Always
Aggregate Standard Deviation			4.51	

Legend: 4.21-5.00- Always; 3.41-4.20- Often ; 2.61-3.40- Sometimes ; 1.81-2.60-Rarely; 1.00-1.80- Never

The extent of receiving teacher practices for students with SEN in inclusive classroom in terms of psychosocial assistance is presented in Table 10. Data shows that item 5 got the highest weighted mean of 4.55 while item 3 has the lowest weighted mean of 4.47 in which

both are always observable practices between the SpEd Teacher and the receiving teachers. In general, the teaching practices in mainstream classroom with regards to Psychological Assistance are continuously apparent with an average weighted mean and a standard deviation of 4.51 and 0.94, respectively. The consistent practice of receiving teacher practices for students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) in an inclusive classroom, particularly in terms of psychosocial assistance, implies a deep commitment to addressing the holistic wellbeing of students. This suggests that both Special Education (SpEd) and receiving teachers actively engage in practices that support the psychosocial development of students with SEN, creating a nurturing and inclusive environment. Recognizing and responding to the unique psychosocial challenges of students contributes to a positive and inclusive learning environment. Teachers can create inclusive environments by promoting a sense of belonging, reducing stigma, and addressing social-emotional needs (Allen et al., 2019).

Table 11. Summary on the Extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN In Inclusive Classroom

Components	WM	SD	Verbal Description
Collaboration	3.77	1.11	Often
Monitoring Progress	4.01	1.06	Often
Pedagogical Support	3.99	0.77	Often
Psychosocial Assistance	4.51	0.94	Always
Grand Mean	4.07		Often
Grand Standard Deviation		0.97	

Table 11 shows the summary on the extent of Receiving Teacher Practices for Students with SEN in Inclusive Classroom. Among the four aspects, the Psychosocial Assistance has the highest aggregated weighted mean of 4.51 which is always displayed as the best practice between the SpEd teacher and receiving teacher in inclusive classroom while the Collaboration, Monitoring Progress and Pedagogical Support with the aggregated weighted of 3.77,4.01 and 3.99, respectively which imply that these often practiced between the SpEd and Receiving Teachers. The frequent practice of collaborative efforts, progress monitoring, pedagogical support and psychological assistance between Special Education (SpEd) and receiving teachers in an inclusive classroom implies a commitment to inclusive education that is responsive to the unique needs of students with Special Educational Needs (SEN). This collaborative approach suggests an awareness of the importance of joint efforts in fostering an inclusive learning environment that supports the diverse requirements of students with SEN. Friend and Bursuck (2002) emphasized the significance of collaboration between general education and special education teachers. The authors argue that collaborative practices contribute to more effective instructional strategies, improved classroom management, and enhanced learning outcomes for students with SEN.

Extent of Receiving Teachers’ Practices

This section presents the level of progress of student with SEN in terms of Affective, Cognitive, and Psychomotor domain which are presented in Table 12, 13, and 14, respectively.

Table 12. Level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in term of Affective Domain

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Has understanding on one’s own emotion, strengths, and weaknesses.	3.94	0.79	Approaching Proficiency
2	Participates and cooperates in classroom activities.	3.66	1.07	Approaching Proficiency
3	Uses courteous expressions appropriately.	4.30	0.88	Proficient
4	Engages in communication with others.	3.91	1.06	Approaching Proficiency
5	Be culturally sensitive and inclusive, displays sensitivity to the feelings with others.	3.96	1.00	Approaching Proficiency
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.95		Approaching
Aggregated Standard Deviation			0.96	Proficiency

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Proficient; 3.41-4.20- Approaching Proficiency; 2.61-3.40- Developing Proficiency ; 1.81-2.60-Beginning; 1.00-1.80-Not Observe/Not Applicable

The level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in terms of Affective is presented in Table 12. Data shows that item 3 got the highest weighted mean of 4.30 which is considered Proficient. However, item 2 received the lowest weighted mean of 3.66 which implies as Approaching Proficiency. In general, the Affective Domain of Student with Special Educational Needs is Approaching Proficiency with an average weighted mean and a standard deviation of 3.95 and 0.96, respectively.

The development of proficiency in the affective domain implies progress in areas like self-awareness, self-regulation, interpersonal relationships, and emotional resilience. This insight emphasizes the holistic nature of education and highlights the importance of creating inclusive environments that consider the emotional and social well-being of students with diverse learning requirements. According to Taylor (2017) that the interventions that focus on social-emotional learning can have a positive impact on the overall development and academic success of students with special needs.

The level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in terms of Cognitive is presented in Table 13. Data shows that item 4 got the highest weighted mean of 3.57 which is considered Approaching Proficiency. However, item 2 received the lowest weighted mean of 3.00 which implies Developing Proficiency. In general, the Cognitive Domain of Student with Special Educational Needs is

Developing Proficiency with an average weighted mean and a standard deviation of 3.34 and 0.93, respectively. The development of proficiency in the cognitive domain implies that the student is making substantial progress in areas such as critical thinking, problem-solving, memory, and comprehension. This suggests that the implemented educational strategies and interventions aimed at cognitive development have been successful, contributing to the student's overall advancement. Given the significance of teacher expectations on students' academic success, it is essential to incorporate the concept of teacher expectations into studies examining factors that impact student outcomes in both regular and special education environments (Klang et al., 2020).

Table 13. Level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in term of Cognitive Domain

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Can recall the lessons that were discussed.	3.30	0.83	Developing Proficiency
2	Can apply mathematical concepts to solve problems.	3.00	0.96	Developing Proficiency
3	Can understand and interpret information.	3.36	0.85	Developing Proficiency
4	Able to read English words and phrases.	3.57	0.90	Approaching Proficiency
5	Able to speak and write his/her thoughts	3.47	1.10	Approaching Proficiency
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.34		Developing Proficiency
Aggregated Standard Deviation			0.93	

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Proficient; 3.41-4.20- Approaching Proficiency, 2.61-3.40- Developing Proficiency ; 1.81-2.60-Beginning; 1.00-1.80-Not Observe/Not Applicable

The level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in terms of Psychomotor is presented in Table 14. All five statements were considered as Approaching Proficiency. Item 1 has the highest weighted mean of 3.83, in which they use fine and gross motor skills to handle objects or perform tasks. However, item 4 has the lowest weighted mean of 3.60 but still considered as Approaching Proficiency which can be noted that a student with special educational needs can work independently in class activities given that such tasks are within their capabilities. The approaching proficiency in the psychomotor domain implies that the student is making significant advancements in activities that involve coordination, movement, and physical dexterity. Collaborative efforts involving teachers, therapists, and parents play a vital role in promoting psychomotor development in students with SEN (Kokštejn et al., 2019).

Table 14. Level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs in term of Affective Domain

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Use fine and gross motor skills to handle objects or perform tasks. Performs physical tasks or actions quickly and efficiently.	3.83	0.92	Approaching Proficiency
2	Demonstrates quick and appropriate responses to situations.	3.64	1.03	Approaching Proficiency
3	Works independently in class activities.	3.47	0.86	Proficient
4	Responds appropriately to sensory input (e.g., touch, sound, taste, smell, visual stimuli)	3.60	1.01	Approaching Proficiency
5	Use fine and gross motor skills to handle objects or perform tasks. Performs physical tasks or actions quickly and efficiently.	3.77	1.00	Approaching Proficiency
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.66		Approaching
Aggregated Standard Deviation			0.96	Proficiency

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Proficient; 3.41-4.20- Approaching Proficiency, 2.61-3.40- Developing Proficiency ; 1.81-2.60-Beginning; 1.00-1.80-Not Observe/Not Applicable

Table 15 shows the summary on the Level of Progress of the Student with Special Educational Needs. Among the three aspects, the Affective Domain has the highest aggregate weighted mean of 3.95 which is considered as Approaching Proficiency while the Cognitive Domain with the aggregated weighted of 3.34 which implies as Developing Proficiency. It is evident from the table that all the domains in terms of affective, cognitive and psychomotor were considered as Approaching Proficiency where there is a Grand Mean and Grand Standard Deviation of 3.65 and 0.95, respectively. The results suggest that the students are making significant strides across various dimensions of learning in which it indicates that the student is not only advancing in cognitive aspects, which involve intellectual skills, but also in affective domains, encompassing emotions and attitudes, as well as in psychomotor areas, involving physical and motor skills. This positive trend implies that the educational interventions, support, and strategies employed for the student have been effective. Collaborative efforts among teachers, therapists, and parents play a crucial role in enhancing psychomotor development and academic achievement in students with special educational needs (SEN), while interventions focusing on social-emotional learning further contribute to their overall development and success (Kokštejn et al., 2019; Klang et al., 2020; Taylor, 2017).

Table 15. Summary on the Level of Progress of Student with Special Educational Needs

Components	WM	SD	Verbal Description
Affective Domain	3.95	0.96	Approaching Proficiency
Cognitive Domain	3.34	0.93	Developing Proficiency
Psychomotor Domain	3.66	0.96	Approaching Proficiency
Grand Mean	3.65		Approaching
Grand Standard Deviation		0.95	Proficiency

Relationship Between Extent of Receiving Teachers' Practices and the Level of Progress of Students with Sen

This section presents the relationship of the extent of receiving teacher's practices towards the level of progress of students with SEN which is presented in table 16.

Table 16. Test of significant relationship between extent of receiving teacher practices and the level of progress of students with SEN

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Result
Collaboration and Level of Progress	0.414	Low Positive	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Monitoring Progress and Level of Progress	0.473	Low Positive	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Pedagogical Support and Level of Progress	0.483	Low Positive	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Psychosocial Assistance and Level of Progress	0.313	Low Positive	0.032	Reject Ho	Significant

significant at p<0.05 (two-tailed)

Table 16 reflects the test on significant relationship between the extent of receiving teacher practices and the level of progress of students with SEN. Using the Pearson product moment correlation test, the result reveals that there is a significant relationship between the extent of receiving teacher practices in terms of Collaboration, Monitoring progress, Pedagogical Support and Psychosocial Assistance towards student's level of progress such as the affective, cognitive and psychomotor domain as p-value yields 0.004,0.001,0.001 and 0.032 respectively which is less than 0.05, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

It can be distinguished from the results that a thorough and cooperative teaching methodology, combined with continuous tracking of student development, specific pedagogical assistance, and psychological support, is suggested to play a key role in fostering the progress of students with special educational needs in inclusive educational environments. Holmqvist and Lelinge (2020) discovered that teachers who participated in professional development trainings developed more positive attitudes towards inclusive education. Moreover, Teachers' competence and attitudes influence their willingness and ability to implement inclusive practices (Pit-ten Cate, 2018). However, achieving successful inclusion of all students may depend on the presence of essential support and resources within school settings (Borg et al., 2011 as cited in Pit-ten Cate, 2018).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, in each aspect—collaboration, monitoring progress, pedagogical support, and psychosocial assistance—the findings support the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that these teacher practices significantly contribute to enhancing students' progress across different domains. It can be concluded that the extent of receiving teacher practices in terms of collaboration, monitoring progress, pedagogical support and psychological assistance would significantly relate to the progress of students with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms. Hence, A comprehensive and collaborative approach to teaching, along with ongoing monitoring of student progress, targeted pedagogical support, and psychological assistance, is posited as having a significant impact on the advancement of students with special educational needs in inclusive educational settings. These findings reinforce the principles of inclusive education by demonstrating that effective collaboration, ongoing progress monitoring, tailored pedagogical support, and comprehensive psychosocial assistance are integral to optimizing student outcomes across diverse domains. By aligning these practices with current educational policies and frameworks, educators and policymakers can further enhance inclusive practices and ensure equitable access to quality education for all students, including those with diverse learning needs. Byrd and Alexander (2020) indicated that teacher education and professional development programs can benefit by providing a continuum of learning opportunities in three important areas: General educators should: firstly, make informed decisions and implement them using accurate assessment data; secondly, cultivate a deep understanding and empathy for students with special needs and their circumstances; and thirdly, develop skills to promote effective communication both within and outside the classroom, involving all stakeholders in the education of these students.

In view of the research's findings, it is highly recommended that the proposed action plan be adopted as a pillar for teachers in providing them with training and professional development in the implementation of an inclusive classroom environment towards the holistic development of student with special educational needs.

References

- Ahmet, Y. (2021). Determining Practices of Classroom Teachers Who Have Mainstreaming and Special Needs Students in Their Classes. *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education*, 9(2), 227-240. <https://doi.org/10.23947/2334-8496-2021-9-2-227-239>
- Al-Shammari, Z., Faulkner, P. E., & Forlin, C. (2019). Theories-based inclusive education practices. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 2(2). DOI:10.31014/aior.1993.02.02.73
- Al-Shammari, Z. N. (2019). Using evidence-based behaviorist instructional strategies with effect size in inclusive elementary schools in Kuwait. *International Journal for Research in Education*, 43(2), 180-208. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:202288103>
- Allen, K. P., Kern, L., & Vorsters, C. (2019). Building a positive and inclusive school culture: Impact on student behavior problems and academic success. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 21(4), 204–215. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203729632>
- Bartak, L., & Fry, J. (2004). Are students with special needs in mainstream classes adequately supported? Perceptions from teachers

in Victoria. *Australian Journal of Learning Difficulties*, 9(1), 16-21. DOI:10.1080/19404150409546750

Bhandari, P. (2023). *Correlational Research | When & How to Use*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational>

Bryant, D. P., Bryant, B. R., & Smith, D. D. (2019). *Teaching students with special needs in inclusive classrooms*. Sage Publications. <https://bit.ly/3stoTeC>

Byrd, D. R., & Alexander, M. (2020). Investigating special education teachers' knowledge and skills: Preparing general teacher preparation for professional development. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 4(2), 72-82. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.2020059790>

Crispel, O., & Kasperski, R. (2021). The impact of teacher training in special education on the implementation of inclusion in mainstream classrooms. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(9), 1079-1090. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1600590>

DepEd Order No 26, s. 1997 – Institutionalization of SPED Programs in All Schools | Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/1997/03/07/do-26-s-1997-institutionalization-of-sped-programs-in-all-schools/>

DepEd Order No. 72, series of 2009. *Inclusive Education as Strategy for Increasing Participation Rate of Children*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2009/07/06/do72-s-2009-inclusive-education-as-strategy-for-increasing-participation-rate-ofchildren/>

DuFour, R., DuFour, R., Eaker, R., & Many, T. (2016). *Learning by doing: A handbook for professional learning communities at work*. Solution Tree Press. https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Learning_by_Doing.html?id=K8quDAEACAAJ&redir_esc=y

Ertmer, P. A. & Newby, T. J. (2013). Behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism: Comparing critical features from an instructional design perspective. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 26(2), 43–71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.19378327.1993.tb00605.x>

Friend, M., & Bursuck, W. D. (2002). *Including students with special needs: A practical guide for classroom teachers*. Allyn & Bacon, A Pearson Education Company, 75 Arlington Street, Boston, MA 02116. <https://www.pearsonhighered.com/assets/preface/0/1/3/4/0134754093.pdf>

Friend, M., & Bursuck, W. D. (2018). *Including students with special needs: A practical guide for classroom teachers (8th ed.)*. Pearson. <https://www.pearsonhighered.com/assets/preface/0/1/3/4/0134754093.pdf>

Global Education Monitoring Report 2020: Inclusion and education: All means all. Paris. (2020). In UNESCO eBooks. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization., Place de Fontenoy, 75352Paris 07 SP, France

Gokbulut, O. D., Akcamete, G., & Güneşli, A. (2020). Impact of Co-Teaching Approach in Inclusive Education Settings on the Development of Reading Skills. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(1), 1-17. DOI: 10.18488/journal.61.2020.81.1.17

Holmqvist, M., & Lelinge, B. (2021). Teachers' collaborative professional development for inclusive education. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(5), 819-833. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2020.1842974>

Klang, N., Göransson, K., Lindqvist, G., Nilholm, C., Hansson, S., & Bengtsson, K. (2020). Instructional practices for pupils with an intellectual disability in mainstream and special educational settings. *International journal of disability, development and education*, 67(2), 151-166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2019.1679724>

Kokštejn, J., Musálek, M., Tufano, J. J., & Kudláček, M. (2019). Parental perceptions of motor competence and physical activity in children and adolescents with developmental disabilities: A systematic review. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 92, 103428. . <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0176556>

Mitchell, D., & Sutherland, D. (2020). *What really works in special and inclusive education: Using evidence-based teaching strategies*. Routledge. <https://bit.ly/461sjmT>

Mjelve, L. H., Nyborg, G., Edwards, A., & Crozier, W. R. (2019). Teachers' understandings of shyness: Psychosocial differentiation for student inclusion. *British educational research journal*, 45(6), 1295-1311. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3563>

Mngo, Z. Y., & Mngo, A. Y. (2018). Teachers' perceptions of inclusion in a pilot inclusive education program: Implications for instructional leadership. *Education Research International*, 2018. 10.1155/2018/3524879

Muhajirah (2020). *Basic of Learning Theory: (Behaviorism, Cognitivism, Constructivism, and Humanism)*. *International Journal of Asian Education*. 1. 37-42. 10.46966/ijae.v1i1.23.

Paju, B., Kajamaa, A., Pirttimaa, R., & Kontu, E. (2022). Collaboration for inclusive practices: Teaching staff perspectives from Finland. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 66(3), 427-440. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2020.1869087>

Paseka, A., & Schwab, S. (2020). Parents' attitudes towards inclusive education and their perceptions of inclusive teaching practices and resources. *European journal of special needs education*, 35(2), 254-272.

Pit-ten Cate, I. M., Markova, M., Kruschler, M., & Krolak-Schwerdt, S. (2018). Promoting Inclusive Education: The Role of Teachers' Competence and Attitudes. *Insights into Learning Disabilities*, 15(1), 49-63. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1182863>

Raguindin, P. Z. J., Ping, L. Y., Duereh, F., & Lising, R. L. S. (2020). Inclusive Practices of In-Service Teachers: A Quantitative Exploration of a Southeast Asian Context. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 9(2), 787-797. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1250412>

Republic Act No. 7277. An Act Providing for the Rehabilitation, Self Development and Self-Reliance of Disabled Person and Their Integration into the Mainstream of Society and for other Purposes. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1992/03/24/republic-act-no-7277/>

Republic Act No. 11650. An Act Instituting a Policy Of Inclusion and Services for Learners with Disabilities in Support of Inclusive Education, Establishing Inclusive Learning Resource Centers of Learners With Disabilities in All Schools Districts, Municipalities and Cities, Providing for Standards, Appropriating Funds Therefor, and for other Purposes. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2022/03/11/republic-act-no11650/>

Saloviita, T. (2020). Attitudes of teachers towards inclusive education in Finland. *Scandinavian journal of educational research*, 64(2), 270-282. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1240894>

Saloviita, T. (2020). Teacher attitudes towards the inclusion of students with support needs. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 20(1), 64-73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12466>

Taylor, R. D., Oberle, E., Durlak, J. A., & Weissberg, R. P. (2017). Promoting positive youth development through school-based social and emotional learning interventions: A meta-analysis of follow-up effects. *Child development*, 88(4), 1156-1166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12864>

Yada, A., & Savolainen, H. (2017). Japanese in-service teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education and self-efficacy for inclusive practices. *Teaching and teacher education*, 64, 222-229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.02.005>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Vexilla Cecilia M. Marinay

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Niña Rozanne T. Delos Reyes

Cebu Technological University – Philippines